

**ENHANCING SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA THROUGH
RELIGIOUS TOLERANCE**

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Abstract

The issue of socio-economic development of the Nigerian nation is a worthwhile exercise that required absolute attention. Economic development as a public sector term, is the process by which the economic well being and quality of life of a nation, region or local community are improved according to targeted goals and objectives. This is measured with indicators, such as gross domestic product (GDP), life expectancy, literacy and level of employment. In an attempt to achieve these objectives, the effects of religious intolerance and violence became the obstacles as it has led to high degree of insecurity and thus devastated socio-economic structures and institutions such as schools, hotels, petrol station, hospitals, shops and workshop and scared away potential investors. Worried by this trend, the work identified lack of religious neutrality on the part of government, lack of religious tolerance, religious fanatics and wrong religious orientation as some of its causes; and therefore recommends amongst others, the need for neutrality on the part of government, upholding the sanctity of the federal constitution that authorized freedom of worship, ban on public preaching in buses and unauthorized places and giving of proper religious orientation by religious leaders to their adherent as panacea.